

IMPORTANCE AND PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING A DIGITAL ECONOMY IN ENSURING ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract: *The key to the success of the achievements of the future is to ensure the consistent and sustainable development of the digital economy, a comprehensive study of important tasks and directions, the development and clear definition of economic development programs at different levels. At present, it is important to draw appropriate conclusions about previous achievements and critically evaluate the results obtained, on their basis to raise the development of the economy of Uzbekistan, to improve the welfare of the people.*

Key words: *digital economy, development, communication technologies, economy.*

The world economy is changing due to the rapid development and increasing use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Although the pace of digital change varies, it affects all countries. This is central to the implementation of the agenda for Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, providing greater opportunities and challenges for developing countries.

From a business point of view, changing all sectors and markets through digitization helps to produce high quality products and services at affordable prices. In addition, digitization alters value chains in different ways and opens new channels for added value and broader structural changes.

The expansion of the digital economy creates many new economic opportunities. Digital data can be used for development purposes and to address social problems, including those related to sustainable development goals (BRMS). That is, it helps to improve economic and social results and can be a force to

increase innovation and productivity. Platforms facilitate transactions and networks, as well as information exchange.

But positive results are not automatic. Since digitization has the potential to support development, it is unlikely that any value performed will be fairly distributed. In the digital economy, individuals, firms and countries may have an indirect negative impact, even if they are not partially involved. Workers with limited digital skills are at a disadvantage compared to those who are better equipped for the digital economy, existing domestic firms face stiff competition from digitized domestic and foreign firms, and various jobs are lost due to automation. The exact impact will depend on the level of development and digital training of countries and stakeholders. This will also depend on policies adopted and implemented nationally, regionally and internationally.

Measuring the digital economy and creating and capturing the appropriate value is fraught with difficulties. First, there is no generally accepted definition of the digital economy. Secondly, reliable statistics on its main components and measurements are not available, especially in developing countries. Although several initiatives to improve the situation are underway, they are still not enough and are struggling to cope with the rapid pace of the evolution of the digital economy.

By definition, estimates of the volume of the digital economy range from 4.5 to 15.5 percent of the world gross domestic product. As for the value added in the field of information and Communication Technology (ICT), the United States and China together make up almost 40% of the total world volume. In terms of GDP share, the sector is the largest in the Chinese province of Taiwan, Ireland and Malaysia. Global employment in the ICT sector increased from 34 million in 2010 to 39 million in 2015, with the largest share (38 percent) falling on Computer Services. During the same period, the share of the ICT sector in total employment increased from 1.8 percent to 2 percent.

In the ICT sector, computer services are the largest component, accounting for 40% of the total value added. The Global computer services industry is

dominated by the United States; its share in the value-added of that industry is equal to the total share of the next nine major economies. India has the largest share in this regard among developing countries. Computer Services, which are considered the only small network growing in all regions, are one of the main factors providing employment in the industry. Value added in ICT production is highly concentrated in East Asia (led by China), and more developing countries may have limited opportunities to obtain value from this sector.

In the last decade, global exports of ICT services and services that can be provided digitally have grown significantly more rapidly compared to exports of General Services, reflecting the growing digitalization of the world economy. In 2018, exports of digitally delivered services amounted to \$ 2.9 trillion, or 50% of global services exports. In the CIS countries, such services accounted for about 16% of the total exports of services, and they more than tripled from 2005 to 2018.

The strengthening of digital platforms leads to global consequences. Digital platforms are becoming increasingly important in the world economy. The total value of platform companies with a market capitalization of more than \$ 100 million was estimated at more than \$ 7 trillion in 2017, 67 percent higher than in 2015. Some global digital platforms have achieved very strong market positions in certain areas. For example, Google has nearly 90 percent of the internet search market. Facebook accounts for two-thirds of the global social media market and is the top social media platform in over 90% of the world's economies. Amazon holds nearly 40 percent of the world's online retail activity, and its Amazon Web Services share the same share of the global cloud infrastructure services market. In China, WeChat (owned by Tencent) has more than one billion active users, and together with Alipay (Alibaba), its payment solution has occupied almost the entire Chinese market for mobile payments. At the moment, it is estimated that Alibaba has about 60 percent of the Chinese e-commerce market.

Global digital platforms have taken steps by strengthening their competitive positions, including buying potential competitors and expanding complementary products or services. Major purchases by digital platform companies include

Microsoft's acquisition of LinkedIn and Facebook's acquisition of WhatsApp. Alphabet (Google) and Microsoft purchased Motorola and Nokia, respectively, and invested in telecommunications equipment. Major platforms have also made other major purchases in the retail industry, advertising and marketing industry, and non-residential real estate.

Other steps include strategic investment in research and development (R&D) and lobbying in domestic and international policy development circles. At the same time, strategic cooperation between transnational enterprises (TMK) and global digital platform corporations in traditional networks is also being studied.

For example, Walmart partnered with Google to use Google Assistant; Ford and Daimler joined Baidu on its Apollo platform; Google created an Android Automotive Platform with Volvo and Audi; GE partnered with Microsoft to use Azure cloud services; and Intel and Facebook are collaborating on developing a new artificial intelligence (AI) chip.

The world economy is changing rapidly as a result of the rapid spread of new digital technologies, which has a major impact on the agenda for Sustainable Development by 2030. Higher levels of digitization of both economies and societies are creating new tools to address global development challenges; however, there is a risk that digital outages will benefit those who are better willing to create and capture value, mainly in the digital age, rather than contributing to more inclusive development.

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